

Age-Standardized Rates Cannot Be Reconstructed into Observed Counts

A Comment on Aarstad (2026)

Ludvig Sjöström

`lud.sjo.06@gmail.com`

Abstract

Aarstad (*F1000Research* 2026, 14:133, v5) analyzes English Office for National Statistics (ONS) data on monthly age-standardized mortality rates (ASMRs) by COVID-19 vaccination status from April 2021 to May 2023, and concludes that vaccination, despite a possible window of temporary protection, may have increased long-term mortality. The paper’s central statistical procedure reduces algebraically to a rescaling of the published rates: the person-years cancel from the pseudo-count construction, so the resulting logistic-regression confidence intervals and significance claims are not valid uncertainty statements for the ASMR-based comparisons. In addition, the “ever vaccinated” exposure definition collapses heterogeneous dose histories; the key inferential comparison is anchored to an especially non-exchangeable reference month; and the supporting citation bundle does not establish what the text claims. ONS has also published an adjusted, individual-level, Census-2021-linked analysis of an overlapping period in the same underlying data stream. That analysis uses non-COVID mortality as a control outcome within a richly adjusted design and reaches different conclusions. The narrower descriptive point that simple ASMR-based comparisons are heavily confounded is valid; the causal claim about vaccine-induced mortality is not.

1 Introduction

The paper under discussion¹ uses publicly available ONS data on deaths by vaccination status in England, aged 10 and over, covering 26 months from April 2021 to May 2023. The author’s stated aim is to illustrate an approach to comparing non-randomized groups in the absence of reliable confounder adjustment, by contrasting all-cause mortality with non-COVID mortality between “ever vaccinated” and unvaccinated individuals. The paper concludes that the data are consistent with a window of temporary vaccine protection against COVID-19 mortality between July 2021 and January 2022, followed by a pattern of relatively elevated non-COVID mortality among the vaccinated that, in the author’s interpretation, suggests vaccination may have increased mortality in the longer term.

I agree with one part of the paper’s framing: simple vaccinated-versus-unvaccinated mortality comparisons in this dataset are heavily confounded and should not be read as clean causal estimates. ONS itself has made essentially

this point.² The purpose of this comment is to explain why the rest of the paper’s argument does not follow from the data, and in particular why the statistical machinery the paper builds around the published ASMRs does not produce valid inferential quantities.

This comment does not attempt to estimate the causal effect of COVID-19 vaccination on mortality in England, and does not take a position on whether such an effect exists. Its scope is limited to whether the specific analysis in Aarstad (2026) supports the conclusions drawn from it.

I proceed in four parts. Section 2 works through the algebra of the paper’s pseudo-count construction. Section 3 discusses the exposure definition and the reference-month problem. Section 4 examines the supporting citations. Section 5 notes the existence of an adjusted ONS analysis that bears directly on the paper’s question.

2 The Pseudo-Count Construction Collapses to a Rescaling of the Published Rates

The paper’s methodological core is a procedure that converts published ASMRs into pseudo-counts of deaths and

¹Aarstad J. *Mortality involving and not involving COVID-19 among vaccinated vs. unvaccinated in England between Apr 21 and May 23*. *F1000Research* 2026, 14:133 (version 5).

²See ONS, *Deaths involving COVID-19 by vaccination status, England*, methodological notes accompanying the release.

populations, which are then fed into a logistic regression in Stata to obtain odds ratios, standard errors, and 95% confidence intervals. The worked example on page 4 of the paper is explicit about the procedure. For each month, let R denote the published ASMR per 100,000 person-years, and let PY denote the monthly person-years reported by ONS. The paper constructs

$$D^* = \frac{R \cdot PY}{100,000} \quad (1)$$

as an “estimated” number of deaths, and

$$N^* = 12 \cdot PY \quad (2)$$

as an “estimated” population, and then runs logistic regression on $(D^*, N^* - D^*)$ as if these were observed binomial outcomes.

The problem is immediate once one computes the implied per-unit quantity:

$$\frac{D^*}{N^*} = \frac{R \cdot PY / 100,000}{12 \cdot PY} = \frac{R}{1,200,000}. \quad (3)$$

The person-years PY cancel. The quantity fed into the logistic regression is therefore just a fixed linear rescaling of the published ASMR and nothing more. The construction does not recover the observed number of deaths from the underlying age-specific data; it merely maps the published rate onto a pseudo-binomial form. The only role of PY is to set the pseudo-denominator N^* , which in turn mechanically narrows the reported confidence intervals around the logistic-regression odds ratios.

This has two consequences. First, the point estimates in Figures 2A and 4 of the paper are not fabricated in the sense of being unrelated to the published data; they are monotone transformations of the published ASMRs and, because the implied monthly probabilities are tiny, numerically very close to simple rate ratios.³ Figure 1 confirms this visually: the monthly rate ratio of unvaccinated to ever-vaccinated ASMRs, computed directly from the published rates without any pseudo-count construction, reproduces the same broad temporal pattern that the paper’s logistic-regression estimates are intended to reveal—high early contrast, narrowing over time, and a mid-period divergence between all-cause and non-COVID series. The derived contrasts in Figure 2B (which uses `xlincom` to compare log-odds from 2A) and the within-group rebasing in Figure 5 (each group’s mortality relative to its own April 2021 value) introduce further issues addressed in Section 3. Second, and more seriously, the standard errors and confidence intervals attached to those point estimates are not valid inferential quantities for the ASMR-based comparisons. A logistic regression treats

³A reader who wanted to compare the published ASMRs directly would get the same qualitative picture by plotting them.

Figure 1: Monthly rate ratios (unvaccinated ASMR / ever-vaccinated ASMR) computed directly from the published ONS ASMRs, April 2021 to May 2023. Panel (a) shows all-cause mortality; panel (b) shows non-COVID-19 mortality. The vertical axis uses a logarithmic scale; the dashed line marks a rate ratio of 1. The same qualitative pattern highlighted by Aarstad’s logistic-regression estimates—high early contrast narrowing over time, with a mid-period divergence between all-cause and non-COVID series—is visible directly in the published rates, without pseudo-counts, logistic regression, or `xlincom`.

its inputs as observed binomial outcomes; here the inputs are deterministic transformations of age-standardized summary rates, not observed Bernoulli trials or observed binomial counts. The resulting 95% intervals are driven by constructed pseudo-denominators rather than the underlying age-specific death counts and the standardization procedure. They should therefore not be used to support any claim of statistical significance, including the claim that the all-cause-versus-non-COVID contrast in Figure 2B is “significant” between July 2021 and January 2022, or that specific monthly odds ratios differ from unity.

Age-standardization compounds this problem.⁴ Running a logistic regression on top of a published ASMR does not undo age-standardization, nor does it yield individual-level inference: it yields a rescaled version of the input.

⁴ASMRs are weighted averages of age-specific rates using a fixed standard population. Within-band heterogeneity and compositional change within an age band can affect the published rate in ways not recoverable from the summary rate alone.

The implication is that the paper’s entire inferential apparatus—the confidence intervals, the significance claims, the use of `xlincom` to contrast log-odds, and the assessment of which months show “significant” effects—needs to be set aside. What remains is a descriptive comparison of published ASMRs, which was already available in the ONS release.

3 Exposure Definition and the Reference-Month Problem

Two further issues undermine the paper’s causal interpretation even if one restricts attention to the descriptive patterns.

3.1 “Ever vaccinated” collapses heterogeneous histories

The paper’s binary contrast pools together individuals with one dose, two doses, three or more doses, recent vaccination, and distant vaccination, across different products and different times since last dose. ONS publishes more granular categories precisely because these groups differ substantially in both composition and COVID-specific outcomes.⁵ Collapsing this structure into “ever vaccinated” can mechanically produce the appearance of waning protection and a “relative increase” in vaccinated mortality, because the composition of the vaccinated group itself shifts over time as boosters are administered to some subgroups but not others, and as people who received only early doses accumulate time since vaccination. This is a known feature of the dataset, not a novel finding about vaccine effects.

3.2 April 2021 is an especially poor reference month

The paper’s Figure 5, which is central to the “relative increase” argument, rescales each group’s monthly non-COVID mortality by that group’s April 2021 value and then compares the trajectories. The author uses this to argue that non-COVID mortality fell substantially among the unvaccinated but remained flat among the vaccinated, and interprets the divergence as suggestive of vaccine harm.

April 2021 was the tail of the Alpha wave, a period of rapid vaccine rollout, and a period during which the composition of both groups was changing from week to week. By that date, the most vulnerable and elderly segments of the English population had been preferentially vaccinated under the UK prioritization policy.⁶ The April 2021 unvaccinated group therefore disproportionately

⁵ ONS notes that risk of death involving COVID-19 was consistently lowest for people with at least a third dose or booster, that the first- and second-dose groups looked more similar to the unvaccinated pattern in later months, and that the corresponding ASMRs are age-adjusted comparisons rather than vaccine-effectiveness estimates because vaccinated and unvaccinated groups differ in characteristics other than age, such as health.

⁶ See the UK COVID-19 vaccines delivery plan and associated JCVI

contained people who had just survived the Alpha wave—a selected residual population—or people who would later be vaccinated and move into the other group. The April 2021 vaccinated group, conversely, was disproportionately composed of the clinically vulnerable and the elderly precisely because those groups had been prioritized.

Figure 2 illustrates this sensitivity directly. When the same non-COVID ASMR series are rebased to alternative anchor months rather than April 2021, the dramatic visual divergence highlighted in Aarstad’s Figure 5 attenuates substantially. The point is not that July 2021 or January 2022 are uniquely correct baselines, but that the visual harm inference is not robust to plausible alternative anchors.

In this setting, the prediction that unvaccinated non-COVID mortality should fall over time is not a prediction about a fixed cohort but about a shrinking, compositionally shifting residual population. Several well-documented dynamic-population mechanisms predict the observed pattern without invoking a vaccine effect: frailty depletion after the Alpha mortality peak; selective movement of frailer individuals from unvaccinated to vaccinated status as the rollout continued; and changing demographic mix of the residual unvaccinated population as younger cohorts became eligible. The paper does not rule out any of these mechanisms. Note 5 acknowledges the compositional issue but dismisses it with a sketch (the “ a versus $a \cdot b$ ” argument) rather than a derivation, and it does not show that the observed pattern is unexpected under dynamic selection alone.

The comparison the paper wants to make—does non-COVID mortality evolve differently in vaccinated versus unvaccinated individuals over time, after accounting for confounding—requires an individual-level cohort design with adjustment for baseline characteristics, which is exactly what an aggregate ASMR-based analysis cannot provide.

4 The Supporting Citations Do Not Establish What the Text Claims

The paper’s Discussion bundles references 24 through 30 as supporting the interpretation that COVID-19 vaccination “can have adverse effects and increase mortality, including from the virus.” Several of these citations do not support that claim.

Reference 25 (Mostert et al., 2024) is an ecological analysis of cross-country excess-mortality trends. It is also an especially weak citation for the specific claim being made here: *BMJ Public Health* later attached an expression of concern, and both *BMJ* and *Our World*

prioritisation criteria, under which older adults and clinically extremely vulnerable people were offered vaccination early.

Figure 2: Sensitivity of rebased non-COVID mortality trajectories to the choice of reference month. Each panel indexes the monthly non-COVID ASMR for each group to 1.0 at the indicated baseline month (dotted vertical line). Panel (a) uses April 2021, reproducing the pattern in Aarstad’s Figure 5: the vaccinated trajectory rises relative to its starting value while the unvaccinated trajectory falls. Panels (b) and (c) use July 2021 and January 2022, respectively. The dramatic appearance of a vaccinated “relative increase” is materially amplified by the choice of April 2021—an especially unstable reference point—as the baseline.

in Data subsequently clarified that the paper does not establish a direct causal link between vaccination and mortality and does not support the claim that vaccines were a major contributor to excess deaths.

References 24 (Fraiman et al.), 26 (Faksova et al.), 27, 29, and 30 (Kelleni) share a common problem: scope mismatch. Fraiman et al. (2022) is a reanalysis of serious adverse events of special interest in randomized mRNA vaccine trials; it does not study all-cause mortality and does not claim to show a mortality effect. Faksova et al. (2024) is a Global Vaccine Data Network surveillance study across 99 million individuals that identifies small excess risks for specific conditions but does not establish increased all-cause or overall mortality. The Kelleni pieces are commentary and perspective articles rather than empirical mortality studies.⁷ None of these references supports the paper’s claim that vaccination “can. . . increase mortality,” and bundling them together creates an impression of corroboration that the underlying sources do not provide.

Reference 28 (Aarstad 2024) is a short ecological analysis by the same author reporting elevated deaths in young people in England in the weeks following vaccination. It is cited as independent support but is the same author’s

⁷Commentary and perspective articles may be relevant to debate, but they do not by themselves establish empirical claims about mortality.

prior work in a different venue. Relevant counter-evidence is not cited. ONS’s bulletin *COVID-19 vaccination and mortality in young people during the coronavirus pandemic* reported that there was no evidence of a change in cardiac-related deaths or deaths from any cause after vaccination in 12–29-year-olds in England.

Reference 7 (Dahl et al.; later published in *BMJ Public Health*) is a Norwegian cohort study used in the Introduction to argue that including control variables made mortality estimates “less accurate” (a 30% crude reduction became a 58% adjusted reduction). The argument assumes what it is trying to show: a larger adjusted estimate is not evidence of greater inaccuracy unless one has already decided the true effect is closer to the unadjusted value. The Dahl paper itself concluded that vaccinated individuals had lower all-cause mortality than unvaccinated individuals, and did not endorse the interpretation that adjustment made the estimates worse.

Reference 1 (ONS Coronavirus latest insights: Vaccines) is used to support the claim that unvaccinated individuals had a worse baseline risk profile “at the outset.” The ONS document does describe demographic and socioeconomic differences between vaccinated and unvaccinated populations. However, the quoted snapshot refers to October 2022, not April 2021. It therefore does not directly support claims about group composition at study entry,

and several of the listed characteristics are demographic markers rather than direct measures of health status.

Figure 6 reference. The paper’s reference 38 for Figure 6 is listed as Our World in Data’s Coronavirus Vaccinations page, but the figure is an excess-mortality chart. That appears to be a citation error and makes the provenance of the figure needlessly difficult to verify.

5 ONS Has Already Done the Adjusted Analysis

The paper’s central methodological argument is that confounder adjustment is either impossible or counterproductive in this setting, and that contrasting all-cause with non-COVID mortality is a useful alternative. What the paper is reaching for has a name: *negative control outcomes*, a well-established design idea formalized by Lipsitch, Tchetgen Tchetgen, and Cohen (2010).⁸ The logic is that if a purported treatment effect also appears on an outcome the treatment should not plausibly affect, that is evidence of residual confounding rather than a genuine treatment effect. In this setting, however, that logic becomes much more informative when paired with individual-level data and rich adjustment. Applied to unadjusted aggregate ASMRs, the contrast cannot tell us whether the observed divergence reflects confounding, selection, misclassification, or a true effect.

ONS has already published *COVID-19 vaccine effectiveness estimated using Census 2021 variables, England: 31 March 2021 to 20 March 2022*, an overlapping individual-level analysis drawn from the same underlying linked-data environment.⁹ That analysis materially pulled the non-COVID estimates toward the null while preserving substantial protection against COVID mortality, especially after the second and third doses.

That analysis does not eliminate every concern about residual confounding; ONS itself notes that some confounding may remain. But it directly undercuts the paper’s framing that confounder adjustment is hopeless and that raw curve contrasts are the best available alternative. The data custodian had richer covariates than were available to Aarstad, used non-COVID mortality as a control outcome in a more methodologically appropriate way, and found that adjustment mattered. The Aarstad paper does not cite or engage with this analysis. A reader of the paper

⁸Lipsitch M, Tchetgen Tchetgen E, Cohen T. *Negative controls: a tool for detecting confounding and bias in observational studies*. *Epidemiology* 2010; 21(3): 383–388.

⁹The ONS bulletin reports models adjusted for age, sex, region, ethnicity, religion, deprivation, socioeconomic classification, education, English proficiency, key-worker status, disability, self-reported health, care-home residence, grouped QCOVID comorbidities, body mass index, frailty, and hospitalization within the previous 21 days, and it uses non-COVID mortality as a control outcome.

would not know it existed. Engaging with it would substantially weaken the claim that confounder adjustment is hopeless and that raw curve contrasts are the best available alternative.

6 What the Paper Does Get Right

For fairness, three points in the paper are sound and worth preserving.

First, the observation that vaccinated and unvaccinated individuals in the ONS data are systematically different at baseline, and that simple comparisons will reflect those differences at least as much as any vaccine effect, is correct. ONS itself says so. This is a useful caution against over-interpreting mortality gaps in either direction.

Second, the early-period logical check—that large baseline differences in non-COVID mortality, at a time when COVID mortality was low, are unlikely to be explained solely by a contemporaneous vaccine effect—is valid and represents a sensible sanity check on the dataset.

Third, the general methodological caution that adding confounders without a causal model can in principle worsen rather than improve estimates¹⁰ is a real point. It does not, however, license abandoning adjustment in a setting where the data custodian has already shown that adjustment is feasible and materially changes the estimates.

7 Conclusion

The paper makes one defensible descriptive point: simple ASMR-based comparisons of vaccinated and unvaccinated mortality in the ONS England dataset are heavily confounded and should not be read as estimates of a causal vaccine effect in either direction. Everything beyond that is not supported by the analysis presented. The statistical machinery consists of a rescaling of published ASMRs dressed as logistic regression, which produces point estimates closely tied to the underlying rate contrasts and confidence intervals that do not provide valid uncertainty statements for those ASMR-based comparisons. The exposure definition collapses dose heterogeneity in ways that mechanically generate apparent waning. The reference-month comparison on which the harm interpretation depends is anchored to an especially poor time point for a dynamic-population comparison, and the paper does not rule out well-documented dynamic-population mechanisms—frailty depletion, selective migration between groups, changing demographic composition—that predict the observed pattern without invoking a vaccine effect. The supporting citations do not establish what they are cited for, and in at least one case they rely on a paper under a publisher’s expression of concern. The paper

¹⁰York R. *Control variables and causal inference: a question of balance*. *Int. J. Soc. Res. Methodol.* 2018; 21(6): 675–684.

approximates the negative-control-outcome idea using unadjusted aggregate data, while an adjusted individual-level analysis using the same logic in a more methodologically appropriate way is not cited or engaged with.

The question the paper raises—whether long-run non-COVID mortality patterns in observational data show anything that standard confounding cannot explain—is a legitimate question, and longer follow-up with finer stratification by age, dose count, time since dose, and vaccine product would be valuable. This paper does not answer it.